

“ WHAT IS THE REPORTED SPEECH AND WHEN
WE USE IT ? ”

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Annotation: This article discusses the Reported speech, how to invert direct speech to Reported speech and its correct use in the sentence. This information is clearly explained in two languages.

Key words: Reported speech, direct speech, say, tell, positive, negative, question, if, whether.

In which cases we can use Reported speech ?

Sometimes someone says a sentence: I am going to the cinema tonight.

Later, may be we want to tell someone else what the first person said. In this situation we use Reported speech.

Bir odamning gapini boshqa odamga aynan o'ziday yetkazish - ko'chirma gap - direct speech. Bir odamning gapini to'ldiruvchi ergash gap shaklida boshqa odamga faqat mazmunini yetkazish - Reported speech.

Here are some things to consider when turning a direct speech into Reported speech.

1. First of all, we pay attention to the type of sentence. It can be positive, negative, question.

2. The next one is, we need to look at the tense of main sentence.

Ko'chirma gapni o'zlashtirma gapga aylantirayotganimizda bo'ladigan o'zgarishlar.

We use a reporting verb like "say" or "tell".

1. Personality change.

He says: I am reading a book.

He says that he is reading a book.

2. Fe'l moslashuvi.

She says: I have cleaned.

She says that she has cleaned.

3. Olmosh o'zgarishi.

He says: I like my cat.

He says that he likes his cat.

Agar bosh gap kesimi Past tense da bo'lsa, quyidagi o'zgarishlar sodir bo'ladi.

4. Zamonlar moslashuvi.

He said: We are working.

He said that they were working.

He said: I have some money.

He said that he had some money.

She told: I have cooked.

She told that she had cooked.

5. Ravishlar o'zgarishi.

She said: My friend is here now

She said that her friend was there then.

Bosh gap kesimi Past simple da bo'lsa Reported speech da o'zgaruvchi so'zlar:

This - that

These - those

Now - then

Today - that day

Tomorrow - the next day

The day after tomorrow - two days later

Yesterday - the day before

Ago - before

Next year - the following year

Here - there.

So, now you have no problem with making Reported speech from positive and negative sentence. But how about questions?

Ko'chirma so'roq gaplarni o'zlashtirma gapga aylantirganda ushbu o'zgarishlarga e'tibor beramiz.

6. So'roq gap tartibi darak gap tartibiga aylantiriladi, kesim, yordamchi va modal fe'llar egadan keyin qo'yiladi.

He asks: Are you waiting for me ?

He asks if I am waiting for him.

7. Umumiy so'roq gaplar if, whether bog'lovchilari bilan bog'lansa, maxsus so'roq gaplardagi so'roq so'zlarning o'zi bog'lovchiga aylanadi.

He asks: Do you work?

He asks if I work.

He asks: Where are the children?

He asks Where the children are.

Agar ko'chirma gap buyruq bo'lsa bosh gapdagi say fe'li tell, order fe'li bilan almashadi. Agar buyruq gap iltimosni ifodalasa, say fe'li ask fe'li bilan almashtiriladi.

Ko'chirma gapdagi buyruq maylidagi fe'l o'zlashtirma gapda to yuklamasi bilan Infinitive holatda ishlatiladi. Bo'lishsiz shaklini yasash uchun Infinitive ning oldiga not inkor yuklamasini qo'yamiz.

He says: Go at once. He orders to go at once.

He says: Don't smoke. He orders not to smoke.

He said: Don't tell anyone. He asked not to tell anyone.

She said: Please, send me the salt.

She asked to send her the salt.

In conclusion, the topic of the Reported speech in English is very comprehensive. In this article we briefly touched on the changes and exceptions

that occur when converting direct speech to Reported speech. I believe that this information will serve as a great source of knowledge for everyone.

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